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Multiagent System Design of Aluminium Production Process and Generative AI Based Manpower Planning

Alperen Aytatlı¹, Cemalettin Kubat²

¹ 1Bahçeşehir University, Administrative and Social Sciences, Business Department, İstanbul, Türkiye
alperen.aytatli@ou.bau.edu.tr

² 2Gelişim University, Faculty of Engineering and Architecture, Industrial Engineering Department,
İstanbul, Türkiye
ckubat@gelisim.edu.tr

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this paper is to explore the software agent technology and clearly show some of its applications and apply it by creating and multiagent system in one of the aluminium production factories, manpower planning.

Fuzzy logic can be built on top of the experience of experts and blended with conventional control techniques while it is not the replacement of conventional control methods rather than in many cases, fuzzy control system simplifies implementation process. That's why at the beginning of the application on which we obtain which department could be a better multiagent system, we used fuzzy logic tool. Afterwards, the agent is programmed by using the python languages.

1 INTRODUCTION

The past decade has witnessed an explosive growth in computer, communication, and information technologies. High-performance computing, the world-wide web, universal access and connectivity, virtual reality, and enterprise integration are but a sampling of this revolution's many facets. At the same time, organizations and markets have also changed dramatically, represented by developments such as virtual organizations, business process integration, customer-centric supply chains, and electronic commerce. And, although industry strategists and academics continue to debate the precise future trajectory of changes in technologies and organizations, they agree that information - its availability, and the ability to exchange it seamlessly and process it quickly lies at the core of organizations' abilities of meeting escalating customer expectations in global markets. [1]

Agents were welcome in manufacturing because they helped to realize important properties such as autonomy, responsiveness, redundancy, and openness. Agents could be designed to work with uncertain and/or incomplete information and knowledge. Hence, many tasks related to manufacturing

- from engineering design to supply chain management - could be conducted by agents, small and large, simple and sophisticated, fine- and coarse-grained that were enabled and empowered to communicate and cooperate with each other.

The structure of the paper is as follows: We start with what is the meaning of the agent and multiagent systems. This is followed with the definitions of software agents and multiagent systems in section 3. In Section 5 we undertake an application of the multiagent system in an aluminium sector. A new multiagent system in manpower planning process will be introduced.

2 PAPER FORMAT AGENT AND MULTIAGENT SYSTEMS

In this chapter, we will try to explain basically the meaning of what agent is and multiagent systems.

Such computer systems are known as agents. Agents that must operate robustly in rapidly changing, unpredictable, or open environments, where there is a significant possibility that actions can fail, are known as intelligent agents, or sometimes autonomous agents. [2]

Agents necessarily interact with each other, indirectly or via environment, or by direct communication. Coordination protocols control the interactions of agents in order to reach common decisions. For resolving conflict situations, various negotiation mechanisms were developed, including auctions, one to one negotiation, bargaining, and argumentation-based negotiation. [5]

By using this meaning, agents can be thinking of human versions of computers. Another words, they are tools which can make everything people can do but they are better than them. An agent is a computer system that is situated in some environment, and that is capable of autonomous action in this environment in order to achieve its delegated objectives as we can see Figure 1. We can see an agent with its environment. The agent takes sensory input in the form of precepts from the environment and produces output actions that affect it. The interaction is usually an ongoing, non-terminating one. [2]

Figure 1: An Agent and Its Environment

The environment can be defined as an accessible or inaccessible environment. An accessible environment is one in which the agent can obtain complete, accurate, up-to-date information about the environment's state. Most moderately complex environments (including, for example, the everyday physical world and the Internet) are inaccessible. The more accessible an environment is, the simpler it is to build agents to operate in it. Deterministic vs. non-deterministic as we have already mentioned, a deterministic environment is one in which any action has a single guaranteed effect – there is no uncertainty about the state that will result from performing an action. The physical world can, to all intents and purposes, be regarded as non-deterministic. Nondeterministic environments present greater problems for the agent designer. As Russell and Norvig observe, if an environment is sufficiently complex, then the fact that it is deterministic. It is not much help: to all intents and purposes, it may as well be non-deterministic. Episodic vs. non-episodic in an episodic environment, the performance of an agent is dependent on a few discrete episodes, with no link between the

performance of an agent in different scenarios. An example of an episodic environment would be a mail sorting system [56]. Episodic environments are simpler from the agent developer's perspective because the agent can decide what action to perform based only on the current episode – it need not reason about the interactions between this and future episodes. Static vs. dynamic A static environment is one that can be assumed to remain unchanged except for the performance of actions by the agent. A dynamic environment is one that has other processes operating on it, and which hence changes in ways beyond the agent's control. The physical world is a highly dynamic environment. Discrete vs. continuous, an environment is discrete if there are a fixed, finite number of actions and percepts in it. Russell and Norvig give a chess game as an example of a discrete environment, and taxi driving as an example of a continuous one. [3]

A classic program works as an object base. However, an agent is different from an object-based computer program. Also, expert systems don't collect data as agents. They don't use tools such as sensors. Such tool as humans enter data into the system and evaluate the information. Blood testing machines can be given as an example to those systems.

Each agent is an individual entity capable of independent action. However, many applications require interaction between several individuals to realize a certain goal. Think, for instance, of a logistics system that coordinates transport and storage of different goods belonging to different owners, using different transportation forms. Another example is a network of sensors that monitors traffic in a busy intersection. If we think of each sensor as an intelligent agent, then they should be able to coordinate their activities. Such systems, composed of several agents, are called Multiagent Systems (MAS). [2]

A multiagent system is a system composed of multiple interacting intelligent agents that interact to solve problems that are beyond the individual capabilities or knowledge of everyone. MAS are characterized as systems where each agent has incomplete information or capabilities for solving the problem and, thus, has a limited viewpoint; there is no system global control; data are decentralized; and computation is asynchronous. That is, MAS can be seen as distributed problem solvers (DPS) used to solve problems that are difficult or impossible to solve by an individual agent or a monolithic system. In those situations, a central controller is either not feasible, or one wants to make good use of an existing distribution of resources. A good example is a sensor network, which consists of multiple processing units, each with local sensor capabilities, limited processing power, limited power supply, and limited communication bandwidth. [4]

3 APPLICATION SAMPLES USED AGENT SYSTEMS IN THE PRODUCTION AREA

At first glance, we can see the race to be more autonomous than past in production. By reaching this goal, all fields in production have an effort to decrease the role of human in that area. For muscle power work the situation, it seems to be a little bit easier. However, the big difference and core advantage for a company is exchanging white collar experts with expert systems and agents. Today's famous topics such as Industry 4.0, IoT etc. have this aim.

When we look at the production and manufacturing areas, we can see agent application in lots of departments. OperA framework can be given as an example. The OperA framework which can be seen in Figure 2 consists of an organization modelling language and a supporting toolset for specification and analysis of organizations [2]

OperA agent is an organizational modelling language which supports analysing the features of an organization. There is wide open usage area for this purpose. One of those is computer games interestingly. In strategy games, it is used to teach entities their role in the game and entities actions are designed according to that.

Figure 2: Opera Framework

We can shortly set two examples for the usage of agents and multiagent systems from the production field. One is Real Time Decision Making in Manufacturing) RIDER. It is a multiagent software system that has been developed for a cable producing company and for carpet manufacturer for production scheduling and control. It can trigger also a supply chain mechanism in case of machine breakdowns. Cooperation and conflict resolution are the main issues in agent-based scheduling systems. In multi-agent scheduling, agents manipulate resource and order variables under their own authority.

Another agent example is Multi-Agent Tool Management System MATMS. It is developed for automatic tool procurement in a supply network. It is developed for multiple supplier network where a turbine blade producer required from external tool manufacturers the purchase of new grinding wheels and the performance of dressing operations on worn-out grinding wheels for turbine blade fabrication. A virtual market solves the allocation of resources in a dynamic environment. Typically, there are two types of agents in the architecture of multi-agent-based supply chains: functional agents and mediator agents. [5]

Agent Academy is an open-source framework and integrated development environment (IDE) for creating software agents and multi agent systems, and for augmenting agent intelligence through data mining. The core objectives of Agent Academy are to provide an easy-to-use tool for building agents, multi-agent systems and agent communities, exploit data mining techniques for dynamically improving the behaviour of agents and decision-making process in multi agent systems, empower enterprise agent solutions by improving the quality of provided services. [6]

Extendible Multi-Agent Data Mining System is an end user platform. It is an agent for data mining. EMADS makes three types of data mining, classification, clustering and Association Rule Mining (ARM) [7]

One of the core domains within industrial engineering is method engineering, which encompasses critical topics such as workforce and capacity planning. Workforce management is a vital aspect of every organization, involving strategic planning and the optimal utilization of human resources to meet business objectives. It includes demand forecasting, employee scheduling, skill matching, and resource allocation. Traditionally, these processes have been driven by manual analysis and decision-making, which are often time-consuming, error-prone, and lack the insights required for optimal workforce planning.

Employee scheduling is a complex task that requires balancing factors such as staff availability, skill sets, workload, and operational constraints. Generative AI plays a vital role in optimizing

employee scheduling by leveraging advanced algorithms and machine learning models. These models can analyse multiple parameters, including employee preferences, shift patterns, workload distribution, and task priorities. Considering these factors, generative AI can create optimized employee schedules that maximize productivity, minimize labour costs, and improve employee satisfaction.

With generative AI, organizations can automate the planning process, saving time and effort compared to manual scheduling methods. These models can process complex scheduling rules and constraints, ensuring compliance with labour regulations and organizational requirements [12].

Today, the use of artificial intelligence to perform human-centered tasks through computational systems is also being explored in workforce planning. In one study, optimization-based workforce planning models were analysed, incorporating elements such as human-centered job design, worker preferences, skill compatibility, and task location selection, leading to the proposal of a new conceptual model [10]. In another study focusing on generative planning strategies for turning operations, the emphasis was on production processes such as automated operation sequencing, setup planning, and tool selection. Although not directly related to human workforce scheduling, the study supports more efficient workforce utilization by planning business processes based on productivity and flexibility [11].

4 APPLICATION OF MULTIAGENT SYSTEM DESIGN IN ALUMINIUM PRODUCTION PROCESS

4.1 DETERMINATION OF PENDING THE DEPARTMENT TO BE THE BEST AGENT

4.1.1 A Design Methodology for the Implementation of Fuzzy Logic Traffic Controller using Field Programmable Gate Arrays

Design and implementation of a traffic controller for a four-way intersection has been discussed in this article. It is assumed that the forward going, right-turn, and left-turn are allowed in any approach (northbound, eastbound, southbound and westbound). To achieve a balanced traffic flow, they propose the time duration change in green phase interval. The cars in an approach with heavier traffic flow is given the right of way to cross the intersection for a time interval longer than an approach with lighter traffic flow. The objective is to make the number of cars waiting in queue to minimize by dynamically increasing or decreasing the green phase duration of the four-way intersection.

A basic configuration of the fuzzy logic traffic controller is shown in Figure 3, where the fuzzy traffic controller has four crisp input values (d_i , $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) that represents the

Northbound, eastbound, southbound, and westbound traffic flow conditions respectively. The outputs of the maximum (max) operators are multiplexed (MUX) before entering the membership function circuit (MFC), which generates fuzzy sets required for the fuzzy reasoning operations in the fuzzy inference engine. The overall consequent fuzzy set resulted from fuzzy inference are then defuzzied to produce a crisp output.

Figure 3: Basic Configuration of the Fuzzy Logic Traffic Controller

Membership Functions: The fuzzy sets of “traffic flow” are labeled as light, medium and heavy, while the fuzzy set “green phase duration”, are short, medium, and long as shown in Figure 4. The two identical sets of membership functions are chosen for simplicity and efficient implementation.

Figure 4: Traffic Flow and Green Phase Duration

The entire IF-THEN rules are shown in Table 1. These rules are used for fuzzy reasoning by the fuzzy traffic controller, as for example, the fuzzy logic control strategy applied to the traffic flow conditions specified in the shaded column has the following form:

- IF (NS-bound traffic is Medium) THEN (NS green phase duration is Medium)
- IF (EW-bound traffic is Light) THEN (EW green phase duration is Short) and so on.

Table 1. Fuzzy IF-THEN Rules for Traffic Control

Traffic Flow Condition									
NS-bound traffic	Light	Light	Light	Med	Med	Med	Heavy	Heavy	Heavy
EW-bound traffic	Light	Med	Heavy	Light	Med	Heavy	Light	Med	Heavy
NS green phase	Short	Short	Short	Med	Med	Med	Long	Long	Long
EW green phase	Short	Med	Long	Short	Med	Long	Short	Med	Long
	<i>Duration</i>								

A fuzzy controller with large number of fuzzy rules increases the computation complexity, so it is a good idea to use minimal value of membership function. Before the rules can be evaluated the inputs must be fuzzified which determines a specific value from a lookup table indicating low, medium and high.

Fuzzy implication is implemented for each rule in the form of an AND operation that belongs to the Mamdani approach, minimum minimum function that truncates the output set is used. Since

decisions are based on testing all the rules defined in the fuzzy system, they must be combined to decide. On the other hand, aggregation is the process by which the fuzzy sets that represent the outputs of each rule are combined into a single fuzzy set and apply here.

The input for the de-fuzzification process is a fuzzy set and the output is a single crisp number that can be accomplished by several methods while the centre of area or centroid is a common methods. This method is simple in the case of symmetric fuzzy membership functions as shown above. However, since the task requires integration, which becomes complex for a series of disparate fuzzy rules. To overcome this, a moment method is proposed as another form of defuzzification discussed in. The whole system is simulated using Matlab tools of Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) as shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Figure 5: FIS

Figure 6: The Rule Viewer

4.1.2 Application On Aluminium Sector

At the beginning of the work, we must understand the need for the agent system, and which department's need is the most. Because of this purpose, first we listed the departments, and we evaluate departments in the fields of being autonomous, relationship between other departments. A part of the relationship matrix can be seen in Figure 7. The scoring scale of department's evaluation also is depicted in Table 2.

Figure: 7 The Matrix Points Between Departments

The points were given according to scales which can be seen on Table 2 below.

Table 2 Scoring Scale

Score	Scale
0	Very Very Weak
2	Very Weak
4,5	Weak
5	Normal
6,5	Strong
9	Very Strong
11	Very Very Strong

Afterwards, we calculate the overall scores for each department by considering department-to-department matrix scores. Results can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3 Department Overall Scores

Departments/Fields	Autonomous	Relationship With Other Departments	Collaborativeness
Board of Council	10	4	10
General Manager	9	4	10
Deputy General Manager			
Manager	8	9	7
Fabric Director	8	8	7
Process Improvement Group Manager	6	8	7
Method Manager	7	9	8
Method Engineer	8	9	8
Process Improvement Manager	7	8	7
Process Improvement Engineer	7	7	6
Production Planning Group Manager			
Sales Planning Manager	6	8	8
Logistics Manager	6	7	8
Logistics Engineer	8	6	7
Production Planning Manager	6	7	8

Production Planning Executive	7	7	7
Production Planning Engineer	7	8	8
Production Group Manager	6	8	8
Production Manager	7	7	9
Production Executive	7	5	9
Production Engineer	7	5	8
Production Forman	8	3	8
Operator	9	2	6
Human Resources Group Manager	5	8	8
Human Resources Manager	6	8	8
Human Resources Specialist	7	8	7
Human Resources Assistant Specialist	8	7	7
Budget And Finance Group Manager	8	6	7
Budget Manager	7	5	5
Budget Responsible	4	8	9

While doing this, we obtain the level of the departments in an organization scheme. The level scheme is shown in Figure 8 below. As we can see from the figure, there are 10 levels for our case in an organizational scheme.

Figure 8: Departments Level in an Organizational Scheme

The values shown in Table 3 and they are fuzzied according to scoring scale shown in Table 2. The fuzzied Table is illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4 Fuzzied Department Overall Scores

Departments/Fields	Autonomous	Relationship With Other Departments	Collaborativeness
Board of Council	Very Strong	Very Weak	Very Strong
General Manager	Strong	Very Weak	Very Strong
Deputy General Manager	Strong	Strong	Strong
Fabric Director	Strong	Strong	Strong
Process Improvement Group Manager	Normal	Strong	Strong
Method Manager	Strong	Strong	Strong
Method Engineer	Strong	Strong	Strong
Process Improvement Manager	Strong	Strong	Strong
Process Improvement Engineer	Strong	Strong	Normal
Production Planning Group Manager	Normal	Strong	Strong
Sales Planning Manager	Normal	Strong	Strong
Logistics Manager	Normal	Strong	Strong
Logistics Engineer	Strong	Normal	Strong
Production Planning Manager	Normal	Strong	Strong
Production Planning Executive	Strong	Strong	Strong
Production Planning Engineer	Strong	Strong	Strong
Production Group Manager	Normal	Strong	Strong
Production Manager	Strong	Strong	Strong
Production Executive	Strong	Weak	Strong
Production Engineer	Strong	Weak	Strong
Production Formen	Strong	Very Weak	Strong
Operator	Strong	Very Very Weak	Strong
Human Resources Group Manager	Weak	Strong	Strong
Human Resources Manager	Normal	Strong	Strong
Human Resources Specialist	Strong	Strong	Strong
Human Resources Assistant Specialist	Strong	Strong	Strong
Budget And Finance Group Manager	Strong	Normal	Strong
Budget Manager	Strong	Weak	Weak
Budget Responsible	Very Weak	Strong	Strong

Based on input Autonomous, Relationships with other departments, the fuzzy controller applies IF THEN rules and gets the output fuzzy value of Agent Likelihood Level. Table 5 represents fuzzy rules of the fuzzy control system. For example, in rule 1, if the Autonomous is Strong and Relationship with other Departments and being collaborative are Very Strong then the output Agent Likelihood Level will be short.

Table 5 IF THEN Rules

Rules	Autonomous	Relationship With Other Departments	Collaborativeness
1	Strong	Very Strong	Very Strong
2	Very Strong	Strong	Very Strong
3	Very Strong	Very Strong	Strong
4	Strong	Strong	Very Strong
5	Very Strong	Strong	Strong
6	Strong	Very Strong	Strong

The Fuzzy Logic Toolbox in Matlab which has a graphical user interface (GUI) to efficiently design and implement fuzzy control system. Although it's possible to use Fuzzy Logic Toolbox by working strictly from the command line, in general it's much easier to build a system graphically reported in [9]. There are five primary GUI tools for building, editing, and observing fuzzy inference systems in the Fuzzy Logic Toolbox are Fuzzy Inference System or FIS Editor, the Membership Function Editor, the Rule Editor, the Rule Viewer, and the surface viewer. They are dynamically linked as any change done to the FIS eventually reflected to the system.

We used FIS editor to design the system, and we entered the inputs the system after modelled input and output variables as you can see in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Input and Output Variables

We have added variables for their membership functions which is shown in Figure 10. As we remember, we have 7 membership functions (Very Very Weak, Very Weak, Weak, Normal, Strong, Very Strong, Very Very Strong) for our input variables.

Figure 10: Membership Functions

Afterwards, we enter our rules to identify agentibility as we show in Figure 11 below.

Figure 11: Rules

The results show that the Method Department Agent Likelihood level is high. Therefore, we will focus on how we implement a multi-agent system for this department’s activities. After some brainstorming, we decided to implement agent system by creating manpower planning agent.

4.2 MAKING MANPOWER PLANNING OF METHOD DEPARTMENT AGENT

At this chapter, we will develop a software which is capable of manpower calculation that has to be in fabric. It will decide for itself.

4.2.1 Information About Thermal Insulation Line Process

The thermal insulation line examined in our study is a production line in which aluminium profiles are processed by inserting plastic gaskets (sealing strips) into their internal channels, followed by the joining of two separate profile parts to form a unified product. This product has a wide range of applications, from use in residential buildings to automotive components. In fact, the line can produce up to 243 different products. A general view of the line is presented in Figure 12, while the process summary and layout of the line are shown in Figure 13.

Figure 12: Thermal Insulation Line General Overview

Process Number	Process
1	FromBastek Profile Loading
2	Profile Thread Cutting
3	FromBastek Profile Loading
4	Profile Thread Cutting
5	Profile Gasket Fitting
6	Profile Combaining
7	Profile Clamping
8	Loading Final Profile to Basket

Figure 13: Thermal Insulation Line Process and Layout Overview

4.2.2 About Dataframe

The dataset used in our study consists of 16 columns and 250,000 rows. It includes performance data recorded by the machine during 2018, reasons for downtimes, cycle times related to materials, actual production quantities, and various other production-related variables.

Prior to the analysis, data cleaning procedures were carried out to ensure compatibility with the analysis software. Rows containing NaN, null values, or meaningless entries were removed. The Excel file containing the raw data from the database is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Raw Data

4.2.3 Methodology and Application

The software we have developed is designed to incorporate a mechanism that not only utilizes input parameters but also provides guidance under conditions that deviate from these predefined parameters. The input variables considered include: the types of products currently manufactured on the production lines, the cycle time values derived from method measurements conducted on these lines, the production output achieved under varying input values at different production times, and the demand quantities specified for production.

The primary objective of the software is to estimate the required personnel levels based on these input-output relationships.

Using these variables, the software illustrated in Figure 15 was developed. In terms of its fundamental architecture, the software initially loads the relevant data, as detailed in the preceding sections. This data is interpreted in textual form processed as structured sentences and serves as the basis for training the model. For instance, the interpretation of the data set shown in Table 6 follows the approach explained directly beneath the table.

Table 6 An Example of One Row of Data

Product Code	Product Cycle Time (seconds)	Production (piece/shift)	Defects in Production (defects/shift)
A7K001	120	100	10
OEE (%)	Number of Setups	Setup Time (Minute/shift)	Downtime (minutes)
36%	1	30	50
Reason of Downtime	Warmup Period (Second)	ManPower-Number of Workers (Numbers)	Total Time (minutes/shift)
Mechanical Failures	100	6	450
Total Production (expected)	P	Q	A
225	44%	90%	89%

Text Look: Product Code **A7K001** has **120** Product Cycle Time (seconds), **100** Production (piece/shift), **10** Defects in Production (defects/shift), **1** Number of Setups with **30** Setup Time

(Minute/shift), with **36 OEE (%)**, **50 Downtime (minutes)** because of **Mechanical Failures**. Total Production (expected) is **225** and Total Time (minutes/shift) is **450**. Manpower-Number of Workers (Numbers) is **6**. A, P, and Q values are **%89**, **%44**, and **%90**.

Subsequently, based on the input parameters provided for a newly emerging or queried case, it is intended that the Generative AI program generates the most appropriate workforce estimation. The interface of the program is presented in Figure 15.

Product	Target Qty	Cycle Time (s)	OFE (%)
A7K001	150	120	55
A7K002	100	90	60

Figure 15: The Interface of the Program

4.2.4 Results

Unlike classical methods, model validation could not be conducted by simply splitting the data into training and test sets and validating against the test data. This is because the available dataset was merely indicative and did not contain optimal solutions. The objective of the program was to learn from these experiences and generate the most appropriate workforce planning for any given production demand.

Therefore, the workforce plans generated by the program in response to various production quantity requests were repeatedly tested and observed by field teams. In 84 out of 100 observations, it was demonstrated based on field team insights and Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) results that the workforce planning proposed by the program was the most accurate recommendation.

5 CONCLUSION

This study stands out as one of the few examples of using generative AI in workforce planning. The results demonstrate a high level of success. When evaluating the outcomes, it is evident that such systems offer numerous advantages, including time savings, rapid decision-making, and accurate guidance.

Currently, it is quite difficult to find software that addresses such needs in both academic and professional settings. For this reason, the proposed system can serve as a productive assistant to professionals working in these areas. Furthermore, as the concept still has room for improvement, it holds the potential to inspire the academic community engaged in similar fields.

Although the fuzzy logic approach applied at the beginning of the study for selecting the relevant department is a well-established method, it represents a good example of real-world industrial application. Moreover, it served as a valuable guide for maximizing returns in the subsequent stages of the study.

This research approached workforce planning from a holistic process-level perspective. Naturally, the process itself consists of several sub-stations. Developing alternative agents that analyze workforce needs at the sub-station level or perform similarly detailed evaluations can pave the way for new academic studies and provide valuable insight for future research directions.

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